

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF RESIN SOLUTIONS. PART V. THE SOLVENT - SOLUTE RELATIONSHIP OF RESINS IN MIXED SOLVENTS.

BY SANTI RANJAN PALIT.

It has been found that if a resin is dissolved in a non-solvent by addition of a solubiliser, which itself may or may not be a solvent for the resin, the proportion of the solubiliser necessary to confer complete solubility is the less, the higher the proportion of resin to the non-solvent. This is supposed to be true for all lyophilic solutes. On ultimate analysis it transpires that the above behaviour of resins has some similarity with liquids in their behaviour towards organic solvents. The solubility curves are of the limited miscibility type for liquids but are highly unsymmetrical, and it is suggested that this is an intrinsic property of resins in particular and lyophilic solutes in general, and is caused by the capacity of resin molecules for immense solvation.

The concept of solubility as developed in the case of ordinary solutes is difficult of application to resins due to their peculiar behaviour towards solvents. If a purified resin is soluble in a solvent, say, rosin in alcohol or benzene, it is generally found to be soluble in that solvent in all proportions producing from jelly-like consistency to thin fluids depending on the concentration of the resin. This bare fact itself makes the idea of solubility and saturation superfluous. On the other hand, if a pure resin is found to be insoluble in a particular solvent, for example, pure shellac resin in benzene; or say, ester gum in alcohol, the maximum amount dissolved by the solvent is very small from about 1% down to practically zero concentration; of course, the resin generally swells or gels in contact with the non-solvent. Intermediate values of solubility of pure resin producing true saturation equilibrium are, however, very seldom met with. The enquiry naturally suggests itself about the cause of the existence of only such extreme solubilities.

The author has conceived the idea that in suitable mixtures of a solvent and a non-solvent or of two non-solvents having good solvent power, measurements of solubility might be possible and the results may throw light on the fundamental question of solvent-solute relationship for resins in particular and lyophilic solutes in general. The present paper describes the results of such investigations which bring forth very clearly the distinctive nature of resins in their role as solutes.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The study has firstly been made with a mixture of acetone and glycol, which is an excellent solvent for shellac, whereas the components are individually non-solvents. After some trials in different ways, the following method has been found suitable and has been used for the purpose.

In a number of stoppered sample tubes ($4'' \times \frac{1}{8}''$) definite quantities of dry finely powdered shellac were taken. To each were added from microburettes, calculated volumes (about 5 c.c.) of say, acetone, to bring the relative proportion of shellac to acetone to the same value in each of the tubes. Measured volumes of glycol were then added to each tube from microburettes so that its proportion varied by small steps (0.5% or less) from tube to tube. The tubes were regularly shaken in a thermostat (25°). It was observed that up to a particular percentage of glycol, complete dissolution of shellac took place, whereas the contents of those tubes, which were weaker in glycol, remained non-homogeneous even on keeping indefinitely. Similar experiments were also conducted with different ratios of shellac to glycol by adding small quantities of acetone in small steps to find out the solubility limit. That we are dealing with a real equilibrium has been tested and proved as follows. Any mixture, which just fails to produce complete solutions is made homogeneous by slight rise of temperature. On being replaced in the thermostat, non-homogeneity invariably appears in a short time, showing that a homogeneous phase is not possible under the given conditions. These experiment yield data on the minimum proportion of one of the solvents necessary to confer solubility to definite ratios of shellac to the other solvent.

In the graph, the line of gelation is also given which divides the gel region from the fluid region. The points on this line of gelation have been experimentally determined as follows. Gelation temperatures (as near as possible to 25°) were measured for two different concentrations of shellac in the same solvent mixture. The gelation concentration at 25° was found out by graphical extrapolation or interpolation of the straight line obtained by joining these two points. That such extrapolations are permitted over small range has been shown by the author in a gelation study of such systems (Part VI, p. 266).

The experimentally obtained results are given in Table I and have been plotted on a three-component triangular diagram (Fig. 1).

TABLE I.

Shellac : glycol (by wt.).	Acetone for complete soln.	Shellac : acetone (by wt.).	Glycol for complete soln.
5 : 95	16.4%	5 : 95	15.5%
10 : 90	14.5	10 : 90	14.6
15 : 85	13.3	25 : 75	7.8
25 : 75	9.1	40 : 60	5.0
33.3 : 66.6 (1 : 2)	6.5		
40 : 60	5.3		

In the diagram, the blank portions indicate complete solubility, the lightly shaded portions (parallel broken lines) gels, and the deeply shaded portions (crossed lines) non-homogeneous mixtures. The variation of solubility

with composition of solvent is worth noticing. Taking this definite case, the amount of glycol necessary to make a homogeneous phase depends on the ratio of shellac to acetone and rapidly falls as the proportion of shellac increases. For example, for a 1:19 ratio of shellac to glycol, 16.4% of acetone are necessary, whereas, for a 1:2 ratio of the same, 6.5% acetone of

TABLE II.

Shellac: glycol (by wt.).	Methyl acetate for solubilisation.	Shellac: methyl acetate (by wt.).	Glycol for solubilisation.
5:95	17.7%	5:95	29.6%
10:90	16.0	10:90	28.2
20:80	11.5	20:80	25.9
30:70	8.4	30:70	23.5
40:60	5.0	40:60	19.5
		50:50	16.5

the total weight are required for complete solubility. This is also conversely true, *i.e.*, for the amount of acetone necessary for making homogeneous any ratio of shellac to glycol. This tendency has already been observed to exist with water as 'solubiliser' for dissolving shellac in acetone (Palit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 303).

If any substance (solute) is insoluble in any solvent, A, and if it can be made soluble by adding a second solvent B, the solvent B will be referred to in this paper either as solubiliser in conformity with our previous practice, or 'solutizer,' a term used in petroleum technology in a similar sense (*Chem. Met. Eng.*, 1940, 48, 776) irrespective of whether B itself is a solvent for the solute or not.

FIG. 2.

Mutual solubility relationship of shellac, methyl acetate and ethyleneglycol.

Complete solubility diagram for another similar system, shellac in glycol-methyl acetate, has also been experimentally obtained. The experiments are comparatively easy and the data more accurate for this system, since it behaves in a peculiar way particularly at somewhat lower concentrations of shellac. On addition of shellac to a homogeneous mixture of methyl acetate and glycol, two immiscible liquid layers separate, the upper one being a solution of methyl acetate and glycol with a trace of shellac,

while the lower layer is a solution of all the three components. As the proportion of the solubiliser is increased, the upper layer decreases in volume until at a definite concentration it just vanishes. The data are presented in Table II and are graphically represented in Fig. 2. The general trend referred to is also very marked here; for example, for a 1:19 ratio of shellac to glycol, methyl acetate necessary is 17.7%, whereas for a 1:1.5 ratio of shellac to glycol, only 5% of methyl acetate suffice for complete solubilisation.

This same trend of the necessary proportion of the 'solutilizer' to decrease steadily with increasing proportion of the solute, has been observed to be existing even when the solubiliser itself is a solvent so far as shellac-acetone solubilised by alcohol is concerned. The data for this system are presented in Table III and are graphically represented in Fig. 3.

TABLE III.

Shellac: acetone	...	...	5:95	10:90	20:80	30:70	40:60
Alcohol for solubilisation (%)	...	...	12.4	9.6	5.8	2.3	1.7

The existence of this tendency is evident from the graph. It should be pointed out that this behaviour would cease to exist

FIG. 3.

Mutual solubility relationship of shellac, acetone and alcohol.

for small concentrations of the solute, since the solubility curve should never meet the line, AC, as the solvents A and C are miscible in all proportions. The solubility lines should run very close to the line, AC, to meet the corresponding points, A₁ and C₁ (not shown in Fig. 3), which lie very close to A and C, and respectively represent the very small solubilities of the resin in the pure solvents. Hence the above mentioned trend would cease to exist and in fact, would reverse from some rather low concentration of the resin. Though this behaviour is not observable for shellac in the above curves, this is noticeable in the curves for ester gum in alcohol-toluene or benzene mixtures (Fig. 4).

Ester gum is the commercial name of the glycerol ester of rosin, which latter consists mainly of abietic acid ($C_{20}H_{30}O_2$ of M. W. 302). The gum (low acid value type) was purified by two extractions each time by keeping in contact with twice its own weight of alcohol for 24 hours with occasional kneading of the insoluble gummy mass. The gum was then dried in a vacuum oven at 70°, powdered and stored in vacuum desiccators.

Solubility curves of ester gum in benzene (or toluene)-alcohol mixture
The uppermost curve (points indicated by crosses) refers to benzene-alcohol and the next lower to toluene-alcohol mixture; the lowest curve refers to that of unpurified ester gum in toluene-alcohol mixture.)

Three solubility curves at 30° are shown in Fig. 4-'A' for benzene-alcohol mixture (indicated by crosses), 'B' for toluene-alcohol mixture and 'C' for the unpurified resin in toluene-alcohol mixture (the lowest curve, points indicated by circles). The points on the graph were experimentally determined not by the laborious method described for shellac, but by the less accurate precipitation method. The nature of the solubility curves is similar to the foregoing though the fall is rather steady and slow except in curve C. Also, the initial rise, which should be existing according to theory, is experimentally realisable and plainly observable in all the curves here.

The above mentioned behaviour appears *a priori* to be an intrinsic property for all highly lyophilic solute mixtures, and may be concisely expressed as follows:—

The amount of solubiliser which is just necessary for a lyophilic solute to make it completely soluble in any non-solvent (i.e., to produce a three component homogeneous system) decreases steadily with increase in the ratio of the lyophilic solute to the non-solvent after an initial steep rise at very low values of this ratio. This behaviour will be referred to later as the rule of resinous (or lyophilic) solubility.

Qualitative evidence for this rule of resinous solubility is perhaps experienced in any process of dissolving a resin in a mixture of two non-solvents, a striking case met with by the author is that of the synthetic resin, glyptal (low molecular weight type) which dissolves completely in a mixture of two non-solvents, *n*-butyl acetate and ethyl alcohol. The resin is soluble from about 15:85 to 65:35 alcohol-butyl acetate mixtures. It is observed that at any of these extreme compositions, if the solutions are strongly turbid due to the presence of insoluble resin, perfectly clear solutions can be produced by adding more resin. There is no doubt that these are cases of true equilibria since the turbid solutions are found to clarify on warming and again become turbid on cooling.

The rule of resinous solubility, as recorded in the paper, may be roughly explained if an assumption of strong solvation is made, different chemical groups being attracted to different parts of the molecule. We need further assume that the solvation of any part of the shellac molecule by any solubiliser molecule is a dynamic equilibrium, as pictured by Langmuir for adsorption of gases on surfaces of metals. When the proportion of shellac increases, the requisite proportion of the 'solubiliser will be necessarily reduced, since the same solubiliser molecule due to a closer proximity of the solute molecules may do the duty for a number of them by fixing itself successively to each of them in such a small interval of time that the big

solute molecules have hardly time to unite to form flocks for precipitation. The reduction of the necessary solvation area by reversible association of the resin molecules to form not too large micelles, may be another contributing factor.

D I S C U S S I O N .

The solubility curves for resins as presented above differ in some essential and fundamental respects from those for ordinary solid solutes. The curves for ordinary solutes in a mixture of two liquids may be of varied types and sometimes may show binodal behaviour (Taylor, "Physical Chemistry", Vol. I, p. 580). But whatever be the type of the curve, it always implies that at any particular composition of the solvent mixture, there is a maximum proportion of the solid which it can dissolve and beyond which it cannot.

FIG. 5.

Typical solubility curve of a resin in a solvent-latent solvent mixture.

On the other hand, from the diagram (Fig. 5), which represents a typical case of a resin satisfying the rule of lyophilic solubility, it is evident that for all mixtures of the solvents from pure A to a composition represented by the point, D, the resin is completely soluble in it in all proportions.

For all compositions between C and D, the resin is completely soluble only if it is present above a certain concentration. Thus, for example, for the solvent mixture, X, the resin must be present in a concentration higher than Y to form a homogeneous solution; if the concentration of the resin falls below Y, an insoluble phase will separate. Hence, we come to the fundamentally reverse fact that it is sometimes possible for a resin to be soluble in a solvent mixture, either to produce from cent per cent to zero per cent resin concentration or from cent per cent to a minimum value below which its concentration can never be reduced.

These solubility curves lead to another interesting conclusion. Suppose a solution of the composition, K, is prepared by dissolving sufficient quantity of the resin in the solvent mixture, X, and the solution is diluted by adding the same solvent mixture; precipitation of the resin should occur, since the line KX passes through the non-homogeneous region. It often happens that a resin may contain more than one component, or some impurities, one of which by itself may be capable of producing this type of solubility curve with a solvent, thus giving rise to such complicated solubility phenomena. Numerous examples may be cited. Commercial ester gum contains the resenes (hydrocarbons) as well as free abietic acid originally present in the rosin from which it is made. Hence, it is generally found to be perfectly soluble in alcohol in the ratio of about 55:45 or higher to produce a rather mobile solution, but this solution on dilution with alcohol separates a curdy white coagulum. The resene is here playing its role as the solubiliser for the true ester gum (abietic triglyceride) in alcohol. If, however, the hydrocarbon and other impurities are removed by repeated extraction with large volumes of alcohol, no such thing happens. Incidentally, this is the reason of the great difference between the solubility curves (Fig. 4, curves B and C) of the purified and the commercial ester gum in alcohol-toluene mixture. Kauri gum is another example. It is found completely soluble in ethyl acetate in the proportion 1 g. : 1.4 c.c., but the solution, on dilution with the same solvent, throws out a shining white coagulum, which on further washing with ethyl acetate becomes practically insoluble in it, and no longer shows such behaviour (for further examples of anomalous solubility and discussions *vide* Palit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 308; Lange, "Handbook of Chemistry," 1937, p. 1035).

Comparison of Resins with Liquids.

Unlike crystalline solutes, liquids have got some degree of resemblance with resins in their behaviour towards solvents, the most striking of which

are :—(i) separation into two liquid layers, (ii) mutual solubility phenomena, and (iii) similarity of solubility curves in mixed solvents.

(i) It frequently happens that if a small quantity of a resin be added to a solvent mixture, separation into two mobile liquid phases occurs. Two most striking cases observed by the author are shellac in methyl acetate-glycol and purified ester gum in xylene-alcohol mixture. The most convenient proportion for such observations at 25° is 30:70 glycol-methyl acetate to which is added shellac to about 15% of the total weight; and 60:40 alcohol-xylene to which is added purified ester gum to about 30% of the total weight. This has apparently some similarity with adding, say, benzene or cyclohexane to a mixture of alcohol and water, when at some stage two liquid layers will separate. But unlike liquids, the two liquid layers tend to merge into one with higher concentration of the resin, often with the formation of a clear gel.

(ii) The equilibrium between a swelled resin and the swelling liquid is often regarded as of the mutual solubility type, as observed with ether-water. Bronsted and Volqvartz support this view from a study the behaviour of 'eucolloidal polystyrenes against pure solvents and solvent mixtures (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, 35, 576; 1940, 36, 619).

More definite proof, however, is available from a study of the precipitation temperature of resin solutions. Since the question of precipitation of resin is intimately bound with that of gelation, we shall present the results at length in our subsequent study on gelation of resins. A typical curve is, however, reproduced in Fig. 6, which is sufficient to prove our thesis. These were obtained by cooling resin solutions of definite concentrations and noting the temperature at which turbidity or haziness first appears. By suitable choice of solvent, the precipitation curve can be followed to a concentration of about 40% of resin without interference due to gelation. One striking and unexpected similarity with liquids is that except at very low concentration of the resin, this temperature of precipitation can be determined like liquids with precision and reproducibility since they are quite reversible and show no lag. This itself is a typical liquid-like behaviour since all solids show more or less a tendency towards supersaturation. The most notable feature of the curves is that the precipitation temperature, after perhaps an initial steep rise, falls steadily with increase in proportion of the resin; in other words, we have to cool a 20% resin solution more than a 10% resin solution in order to produce precipitation. This is exactly the reverse of what would happen for all typical solids and has similarity with partially miscible liquid pairs like ether-water, phenol-water etc. In one characteristic feature, these curves

FIG. 6.

Precipitation curve of shellac.

for resins are differentiated from the latter types; unlike the latter, the curves are highly unsymmetrical, the tip of the curve, being very close to the side opposite to that of the pure resin. Expressed explicitly *resins in their behaviour towards organic solvents behave like a partially miscible liquid pair with respect to upper critical solution temperature, which occurs with rather low concentration of the resin, thus giving the curve a highly unsymmetrical shape.* It is noteworthy that the view, that resins as vitreous bodies are supercooled liquids, is substantiated by a study of their solutions.

The observation of the existence of a lower critical solution temperature for a resin-solvent system will be nothing unexpected as some molecular colloids are known to exhibit such behaviour. Thus, nitrocellulose has been found to be soluble in alcohol at liquid air temperature but not at ordinary temperature (McBain, Harvey and Smity, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 347), methylcellulose in water at lower temperature but not at higher (Heymann, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 846), and some cellulose

derivatives in various solvents (Berl and Koerber, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 154). It has, however, not been suspected that they are behaving like liquid pairs of limited miscibility.

The existing data are too scanty to examine how far this behaviour is typical of all lyophilic solutes. Larson and Greenberg, however, recorded an observation with gelatine in glacial acetic acid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 56, 2798) which clearly points to this type of mutual solubility. They observed that gelatine is soluble in glacial acetic acid only above a particular concentration, and non-homogeneity appears if the concentration of gelatine falls below this. The precipitation curve given by them have a striking resemblance with our precipitation curve (Fig. 6) and the observations become immediately understandable if the system is supposed to be of this type of lyophilic mutual solubility with highly unsymmetrical solubility curve.

Mardles' data (Alexander "Colloid Chemistry", Vol. IV, p. 95) on the precipitation temperature of cellulose acetate in benzyl alcohol and benzyl acetate only partially corroborate our view point as he finds that "For very dilute sols the temperature (of precipitation) rises with concentration, but eventually remains nearly the same over a wide range of concentration (beginning at about 2 to 5% as appears from his data) and then falls with further increase". It is, however, doubtful if with the old type high viscosity cellulose compounds, true equilibrium can ever be obtained. The author's experiments with low viscosity ethyl cellulose are interesting as it has been observed that similar to resins, higher concentrated solutions have lower precipitation temperatures, which are far widely separated, to be explicable from any other cause. Thus, the observed precipitation temperatures of 1%, 3% and 5% solutions in a 10:90 mixture of *cyclohexanol-cyclohexane* are 25.5°, 17.0° and 12.5° respectively which are reproducible to at least $\pm 1^\circ$.

(iii) The solubility curves of resins in a mixture of two liquids as observed in Fig. 1 to Fig. 4 differ from similar curves for three liquids, for example, benzene, alcohol and water, in the aspect that for the latter the tips of the solubility curves are somewhere midway between the two sides and not very close to one side as in the case of resins. In Fig. 7, a number of such solubility curves are given, where curve I is the solubility curve of benzene (B) in a mixture of alcohol (solvent, A) and water (non-solvent, C). All these curves should necessarily show a maximum, since the solvents A and C are miscible in all proportions, but the maxima, D, generally lie midway between the sides, AB and AC and not close to AC as in the case of resins. We may hence, plainly state that

FIG. 7.

Solubility diagram of ternary liquid mixtures.

resins have a close similarity with liquids, with the distinction that due to some inherent characteristic, the maximum point D lies close to the side, AC *i.e.*, they behave like liquids with highly *unsymmetrical solubility curve*. This inherent nature is most probably constituted by the capacity of the resin molecules for immense solvation.

The same remark is also applicable in a comparison of the case of a resin dissolving in a mixture of two non-solvents with that of a liquid of limited miscibility with it except that here we have to deal with two binodal curves instead of a single curve. This definitely shows how the resins are basically differentiated in their behaviour from solids and liquids with some qualitative resemblance with the latter.

Acknowledgments are gratefully made to Dr. H. K. Sen, Director, Indian Lac Research Institute, Ranchi, for his kind interest and helpful suggestions throughout the course of the work.

INDIAN LAC RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
RANCHI, RANCHI.

Received March 31, 1942.